

IMPROVED INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS FOR VINYL ESTER RESIN - FIBRE GLASS COMPOSITES

Peter J. Burchill and Gary J. Simpson

*Ship Structures and Materials Division,
Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory, DSTO,
PO Box 4331, Melbourne, Victoria 3001, Australia.*

SUMMARY: Toughening the matrix using modified acrylonitrile - butadiene copolymers improves the delamination resistance of vinyl ester resin - glass woven roving composites. Analysis of the largest (or smallest) measurements of toughness by extreme value theory shows that the improvement to the matrix resin is fully transferred to the composite. The glass content of the composite does not appear to determine the delamination resistance for contents of 38 - 70 vol%. For the composites used in this study the contribution to interlaminar fracture toughness by the reinforcement ranges from 0 to 1400 Jm⁻².

KEYWORDS: delamination resistance, extreme value theory, vinyl ester resins, acrylonitrile / butadiene copolymers, woven glass roving reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

Fracture in cloth - resin composites occurs most easily parallel to the reinforcement between the layers of cloth resulting in delamination of the composite and a large reduction in compressive strength. Generally tensile loading produces this delamination, and the cracks grow at the fibre-matrix interface or through failure of the matrix resin, or a combination of both. Improvement of the fracture toughness of composite structures will require the suppression of this crack growth. Most studies of fracture in composites have looked at unidirectional fibre - epoxy resin based materials [1], but vinyl ester resin composites are just as prone to delamination which is governed by the brittle nature of the matrix and the fibre - matrix bond. From previous studies, two energy absorbing mechanisms can be identified contributing to the delamination resistance; energy is absorbed by deformation of the resin or by the effects of fibres bridging the crack [2-6]. Bridging fibres absorb energy through their being pulled out of the matrix and through fracture. Another mechanism by which the fracture energy may be increased is by crack deflection which may arise due to imperfections in the composite or through local changes in fibre orientation, that will be experienced with cloth - based composites.

Vinyl ester resins (VE) are typically a mixture of methacrylate esters produced from epoxy resins diluted with other monomers such as styrene and are generally cured at room temperature to give materials with a much higher resistance than polyester resins to moisture and corrosive chemicals. A commonplace VE resin is made from the diglycidylether of bisphenol A and is the work horse of the vinyl ester resin market. A feature which gives these

resins a strong advantage over epoxy resins apart from price is that they can be formulated to provide almost any desired pot-life. Studies of the properties of bulk castings show them to be brittle, however recent work on toughening has shown that large improvements in toughness can be gained by the addition of suitable reactive liquid polymers (RLP) which yield a separated elastomeric phase upon cure [7,8]. This study will examine how well the improvement in resin bulk properties transfer to VE resin / glass fibre composites.

The hand lay-up and vacuum bagging method of composite fabrication was suspected of not being very reproducible in terms of glass to resin ratio, in addition, toughened resins have a higher viscosity which will affect resin wet-out and flow in the preparation of the composite. Hence, no attempt was made to control the glass content, but rather allow deliberate variation in the process to give a glass to resin ratio which was as wide as practicable between composites. In this way, a more confident comparison was expected of the influence different resins have on composite toughness. This approach was hoped would also provide data on the fibre bridging and weave effects of the reinforcement which were suspected of being influenced by resin content.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two vinyl ester resins used were: Derakane® 411 (Der 411) a standard bisphenol A epoxy based vinyl ester resin, and Derakane® 8084 (Der 8084) a toughened version of Der 411 internally modified with a reactive acrylonitrile - butadiene copolymer during manufacture. The additives were: a vinyl terminated acrylonitrile - butadiene copolymer (BF Goodrich VTBN X33) and a BF Goodrich carboxy terminated acrylonitrile - butadiene copolymer pre-reacted with an aliphatic oligomeric epoxide (S22) [9]. The reinforcement was a woven roving - AR106, Colan Products Pty. Ltd., nominal areal density 630 g/m² - with a vinyl ester resin compatible finish. The structure of the cloth was warp 29.5 yarns per 10cm, 1200 tex., and weft 15.8 yarns per 10cm, 1800 tex. All other materials were commercial chemicals used as received.

Resin Cure and Composite Fabrication

The resins and their blends with the additives were cured at room temperature using the catalyst system cobalt octoate (0.3 pph, of a 41% wt/vol solution in white spirit) and methylethylketone peroxide (1.5 pph, of a 40% dimethyl phthalate solution), and the gel time was adjusted with dimethylaniline (accelerator) and 2,4-pentanedione (retarder). Curing of all resin systems was completed overnight at room temperature then for 90 minutes at 90°C. The test methods used for evaluating bulk properties were, Heat Distortion Temperature (ASTM D648), T-Peel (ASTM D1876) and fracture toughness from double torsion geometry [10].

Various techniques were used to alter the glass : resin ratio in the hand lay-up/vacuum bagging method, involving timed application of vacuum, and pot formulations to change gel times. The composite panels were assembled with 16 plies of cloth (300mm x 500mm) cut with the warp direction measuring 300mm. A thin Teflon® film was placed as a de-bond zone between the 8th and 9th plies to give an initial crack of about 50mm in the test specimens.

Fracture Resistance

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens (25 x 190mm) with the long axis parallel to the warp direction were cut from the composite panels with the de-bond layer at one end. To load the specimen, tabs were attached to the de-bond end; and one side of the specimen was painted with whitener to aid observation of the crack and marking its length. The specimen was carefully put under a tensile load to open the de-bonded zone and pre-cracked to about 52 mm from the beginning. The specimen was then unloaded to its original position, and the Instron Testing Machine (Model 4502) set at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. When a pre-determined crosshead displacement was reached, the specimen was unloaded by about 5% of the displacement before marking the crack length. The first measurement was generally between 60 to 75 mm from the open end of the beam. The corresponding load and displacement before the unloading were recorded automatically by the computer. Further measurements were taken until 12 measurements (excluding the initial crack length) were recorded. After the test, the specimen was unloaded and crack lengths were measured using a travelling microscope with all measurements taken from the tab-end.

Load (P), displacement (d) and crack length (a) data were analysed by two methods, one due to Hashemi, Kinloch and Williams [11] and another due to Rosensaft [12]. Both methods of data reduction gave essentially the same values for fracture toughness and the values reported here are from analysis using equations given by Hashemi et al.

Compliance ($C = P/d$) is related to specimen dimensions and material properties by:

$$C = 8N \cdot \frac{(a + \chi h)^3}{Bh^3 E_{11}} \quad (1)$$

N is a correction factor which accounts for the stiffening effects of the attachments required to load the specimen and corrections due to large displacements and attachment tilting, other symbols are: thickness 2h, width B, modulus E_{11} . The term χh , adjusts the measured crack length for compliance of the un-cracked part of the specimen [11,13,14].

Strain energy release rate (G_I) is calculated from:

$$G_I = (F/N) \cdot 3P\delta / 2B(a + \chi h) \quad (2)$$

F is a factor which corrects for the shortening of the crack length due to large displacements. Equations for F and N can be found in references [11,14].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matrix Resins

The ability of the rubber additives to improve adhesion and crack resistance of the vinyl ester resin Der 8084 is detailed in Table 1. A marked improvement in peel strength is achieved by the addition of either rubber, and similar improvements are seen in the fracture energy of the castings. The lowering of HDT due to the rubber should also be noted, and is an unfortunate consequence of rubber toughening of any type of resin

Table 1: Properties of the resin systems

Resin	Additive	Fracture Energy kJ/m ²	Peel Strength N/mm	HDT °C
411	NONE	0.13	0.5	101
8084	NONE	0.4	0.9	80
8084	6.86% X33	1.40	2.31	73
8084	6.86% S22	2.40	3.01	70

Composite Properties

A minimum of five specimens was tested from each composite panel, and from each specimen generally twelve measurements of toughness were obtained as the crack propagated between the plies. Load deflection curves for these composites showed that crack growth generally progressed by stick / slip with some continuous slow crack growth regions which were greater in extent with toughened matrix resins.

Fig. 1: Toughness measurements on Der 8084 + X33 composite specimens

Despite the uniformity with which a particular composite was made, it was apparent early in the project that the specimens were not the same, and there was a wide variation in calculated toughness values in one specimen associated with crack initiation and arrest. Fig. 1 gives the toughness values from the five specimens of a Der 8084 + X33 composite. The values for each specimen have been placed in serial order and is not the order in which they were determined, toughness measurements did not depend on position along the specimen.

An analysis of variance showed that the specimens were not identical, and a similar result was found for all the composite panels. Nevertheless, if the compliance measurements for each specimen are normalised for variation in thickness and width, and plotted as the cube root against crack length, all the values fall on a common line as seen in figure 2, and as expected if equation 1 was obeyed. The slope of this line is $(8/E_{11})^{1/3}$.

Fig. 2: Compliance data for all specimens tested from a Der 8084 + S22 composite

This agreement in modulus for the specimens from one panel indicates that the variation in toughness is not due to poor fabrication of the panel. The average toughness determined from a composite specimen was always greater than the toughness of the neat resin.

Figure 3 gives a plot for each resin type of the observed average specimen toughness against specimen thickness. Thickness is a function of the glass content which for these composites varied between 38 and 70 volume %, and each line is constructed from measurements on at least four composite panels.

Fig. 3: Variation of toughness with specimen thickness

These results show that there is an increase in toughness of a composite with increase in resin toughness, however, the scatter makes the difference difficult to quantify. The slopes of these lines suggests that there is little or no dependence on glass content. Thus the variation in interlaminar toughness of these composites seems to be determined wholly by the conditions along the plane which the crack is forced to follow. These conditions appear not to be determined by a global glass to resin ratio. Previous work ascribes the toughness of a composite as being determined by the toughness of the resin and by fibre bridging effects [2-6]. Improvements to resin toughness have been said not to be fully transferred to a composite, and that there was a limit above which the benefits of further toughening of the matrix were marginal [3,4].

Extreme Value Analysis

An alternate analysis of the results has been carried out applying extreme value theory [15,16]. Firstly, because of the very weak dependence on glass content the results from all the composites made from a particular resin were pooled, and the values from each specimen ordered from smallest to largest. Thus from the four composites made with Derakane 411, twenty smallest (or largest) values of toughness were obtained which were again ranked in increasing order. These values have been presented as a Gumbel plot in figure 4, in which the ordinate scale is a function of the cumulative probability ($F(x)$) defined as $i/(n+1)$ where i is the rank of a particular value, and n is the total number of values.

This figure represents the cumulative probability of observing a toughness less than or equal to a given value, and the linearity of the plot indicates a reasonable fit to the Gumbel distribution - a Type 1 asymptotic distribution of smallest or largest extremes. Data from Der 8084 composites are also displayed, and the differences between these two curves probably reflects different interactions of the resin with the reinforcement

Fig 4: Probability plot of maximum toughness recorded for each specimen

Fig. 5 shows the Gumbel plot for the maximum specimen toughness values for Derakane 8084 blended with S22, and compared with the values obtained from composites with the untoughened resin. Here the advantages of toughening the resin is clearly seen, the offset between the curves is similar to the change in toughness of the neat resin when blended with the additive. Likewise, a plot for Der 8084 + X33 composites gave the improvement to the toughness as an offset of about 1.1kJm^{-2} . These plots also indicate that the probability of having a toughness less than a specified value is much reduced for composites made with the modified resin.

Fig. 5: Probability plot of effect of resin toughening on composite delamination

Because the crack growth behaviour in these composites was seen to be a stick - slip process, then the maximum values observed for each specimen are most likely to be for crack growth initiation. The wide range of these values would then seem to be associated with the varying effects of crack pinning by the glass filaments and from crack deflection as a result of following the undulating surface of the cloth. The smallest of these maximum values could be as a result of initiation from resin rich areas within the composite. Comparison with the largest values then gives a measure of the contribution due to glass fibres and the structure of the cloth.

Table 2 lists these smallest and largest values for the four resin systems, and from the above assumptions the difference gives how much this particular glass cloth might contribute to toughness in a composite. This contribution is thus about 0 to 1.4kJ m⁻² in addition to the toughness of the resin for Der 8084 based composites. Except for the Der 8084 + S22 matrix, the smallest values are much larger than the toughness of the unreinforced resins especially in the case of Der 411, and shows that these values also have a contribution from the reinforcement.

Table 2: Smallest and largest values of the observed maximum toughness

Composite Matrix	Smallest Maximum (kJ m ⁻²)	Largest Maximum (kJ m ⁻²)	Contribution by Glass Cloth (kJ m ⁻²)
Der 411	0.76	1.60	0.84
Der 8084	0.69	2.05	1.36
Der 8084 + X33	1.70	3.19	1.49
Der 8084 + S22	2.47	3.80	1.33

CONCLUSIONS

The delamination resistance of vinyl ester resin - glass woven roving composites can be greatly improved through toughening the resin. Scatter in the results and the use of average values hides the true advantage of using a toughened resin in a composite to improve interlaminar fracture resistance. However by applying extreme theory to the largest (or smallest) toughness values recorded from each test specimen, the benefits of increased resin toughness becomes much more apparent. For the resin systems used, the improvement to the resin is clearly transferred to the composite. The reinforcement also contributes a variable amount to the delamination resistance which appears to be between 0 and 1400 Jm⁻². Global variation in glass content does not appear to be a factor in determining this reinforcement contribution.

REFERENCES

1. Martin, R.H., "Interlaminar Fracture Characterization: A Current Review", *NASA -CR-187573*, 1991.
2. Slepetz, J.M. and Carlson, L., in 'Fracture Mechanics of Composites', *ASTM Special Technical Publication 593*, 1975, p.143.
3. Bascom, W.D., Bitner, J.L., Moulton, R.J. and Siebert, A.R., "The interlaminar fracture of organic-matrix woven reinforcement composites", *Composites* 1980, 9

4. Hunston, D.L., "Composite Interlaminar Fracture: Effect of Matrix Fracture Energy", *Compos. Technol. Rev.*, Vol. 6, 1984, p. 176.
5. Huang, X.N. and Hull, D., "Effects of fibre bridging on G_{Ic} of a unidirectional glass / epoxy composite", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol 35, 1989, p. 283.
6. Briscoe, B.J. and Williams, D.R., "Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of Aramid/Epoxy Laminates", *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol. 46, 1993, p. 277.
7. Pham, S. and Burchill, P.J., "Toughening of Vinyl Ester Resins with Modified Polybutadienes", *Polymer*, Vol. 36, 1995, p. 3279.
8. Burchill, P.J. and Pearce, P.J., "Epoxy Acrylate - Based Resins", *Polymeric Materials Encyclopedia*, Vol. 3, Salamone, J.C., Ed., CRC Press Inc., 1996, 2204.
9. Material synthesised by P.J. Pearce according to information provided by BF Goodrich.
10. Kies, J.A., and Clark, B.J., "Fracture propagation rates and times to fail following proof stress in bulk glass", *Fracture 1969*, Ed., Pratt, P.L., (Chapman and Hall, London, 1969), p. 483.
11. Hashemi, S., Kinloch, A.J. and Williams, J.G., "The analysis of interlaminar fracture in uniaxial fibre-polymer composites", *Proc. Royal Soc.*, Vol. A427, 1990, p. 173.
12. Rosensaft, M. and Marom, G., "A one Specimen Mode I Delamination Test for Composite Materials", *J. Comp. Tech. Res.*, Vol. 10, 1988, p. 114.
13. Kanninen, M.F., "An Augmented Double Cantilever Beam Model for Studying Crack Propagation", *Int. J. Fracture*, Vol. 9, 1973, p. 83.
14. Williams, J.G., "The Fracture Mechanics of Delamination Tests", *J. Strain Anal.*, Vol. 24, 1989, p. 207.
15. Gumbel, E.J., "Statistics of Extremes", Columbia University Press, New York, 1966.
16. Mann, N.R., Schafer, R.E. and Singpurwalla, N.D., "Methods for Statistical Analysis of Reliability and Life Data", John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York, 1974.